

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part XIV. Synthesis and *in vitro* Antimicrobial Study of Some 3-methyl-5-(*p*-alkylphenyl)-4-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) Pyrazoles

C. MOHAN†, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

Manuscript received 2 April 1976; accepted 28 May 1976

A number of 3-methyl-5-*p*-alkylphenyl-4-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles have been synthesised by condensing different 1-(*p*-ethyl/methylphenyl)-3-methyl-2-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine and thiosemicarbazide. On screening *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* a large number of these exhibit considerable activity.

IN an attempt to study the structure-activity relationship amongst the azole derivatives, we have already reported the synthesis and antibacterial activity of some 3,5-diaryl- and 3-methyl-5-*p*-alkoxy/halophenyl-4-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles¹⁻⁵ and isoxazoles⁶. This study has revealed that the antibacterial activity increases as the electronegativity of the halogen atom present in the phenyl ring attached at position-5 decreases and among the alkoxy groups, the activity decreases with the increase in the size of the group and the compounds having the methoxy group were found to be the most active. These results tempted us to synthesise some compounds of this class by introducing the alkyl groups in the phenyl ring attached at position-5 with a view to (a) study the effect of the alkyl group on the antibacterial properties of the pyrazoles and (b) compare these results among themselves as well as with those obtained earlier^{3,6}. The purity and homogeneity of these compounds was tested by TLC and elemental analysis.

Experimental

The different 1-*p*-alkylphenyl-3-methyl-2-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones required for this work were prepared following the procedure already reported.⁷

Synthesis of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-(p-methylphenyl)-4-(p-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles :

Phenylhydrazine (0.05 g) was added to a solution of 1-(*p*-methylphenyl)-3-methyl-2-(*p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-dione (0.1 g) in a mixture of glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and ethanol (5 ml) and the contents refluxed in a water bath for 6-7 hr and then

left overnight. The solid which separated out was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol-glacial acetic acid mixture in yellowish-orange needles, m.p. 278°. (Yield : 0.09 g; 73%). (Found : C, 64.2; H, 5.0. C₂₃H₂₁O₂N₂S requires : C, 64.0; H, 4.9%).

Reactions with thiosemicarbazide and hydrazine hydrate (100%) were carried out in the manner reported earlier³.

Similar set of reactions was carried out with 1-(*p*-ethylphenyl)-3-methyl-2-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones.

Antibacterial activity :

All the pyrazole derivatives were screened⁸ *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and these indicated mixed activity. In the *N*¹-unsubstituted pyrazoles activity increases with the size of the alkyl group when present in the phenyl ring attached at position-5 and this enhancement in activity is greater against *E. coli* as compared to *S. aureus*. On the other hand, the introduction of a phenyl group, *N*' of the pyrazole ring causes a decrease in the activity against both the organisms. It is further noticed that the pyrazoles having the 5-methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl group exhibit highest activity irrespective of other substituents. When these results are compared with those obtained earlier it is clear that the replacement of the halogen atom by the alkyl group causes a decrease in activity with only few exceptions and when compared with those having the alkoxy group, the activity is of a much lower order.

All the synthesised pyrazoles along with the results of their screening are entered in Tables 1 and 2.

† Deceased.

TABLE 1—3-METHYL-5-(*p*-METHYLPHENYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENE AZO) PYRAZOLES

(Ar = *p*-methylphenyl)

S.No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
R₁ = H							
1.	H	268	O	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₅ S	—	—
2.	Acetyl	238	O	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₅ S	—	—
3.	Phenyl	197	YO	71	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₅ S	+	—
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	157	YO	70	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₅ S	+	+
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	160	O	72	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₅ S	+	+
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	203	O	71	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₅ S	+	—
7.	Guanidyl	310	O	80	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₇ S	+	—
8.	α -Pyridyl	263	O	72	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₆ S	—	+
9.	Pyrimidyl	268	O	74	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₇ S	—	+
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	183	O	73	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₇ S	+	—
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	245	R	72	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₇ S	+	—
12.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	271	YO	74	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₇ S ₂	+++	+
13.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	210	Y	71	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₆ S	—	—
R₁ = Ph							
14.	H	278	YO	73	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₅ S	—	—
15.	Acetyl	285	Y	71	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₅ S	—	+
16.	Phenyl	208	O	70	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₅ S	—	—
17.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	230	B	69	C ₃₀ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₅ S	—	—
18.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	229	R	69	C ₃₀ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₅ S	+	—
19.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	218	O	70	C ₃₀ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₅ S	—	—
20.	Guanidyl	242	YO	75	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₇ S	+	—
21.	α -Pyridyl	228	R	71	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆ S	+	—
22.	Pyrimidyl	203	OR	75	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₇ S	+	—
23.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	205	R	72	C ₂₉ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₇ S	—	—
24.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	198	O	71	C ₂₉ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₇ S	+	—
25.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	235	YO	73	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₇ S ₂	+++	+
26.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	275	Y	70	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ O ₃ N ₆ S	—	—
R₁ = Thiocarbamido							
27.	H	260	R	75	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	—	—
28.	Acetyl	256	O	74	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	+	+
29.	Phenyl	220	O	73	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	—	—
30.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	182	Y	71	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	+	—
31.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	185	O	74	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	+	—
32.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	207	Y	75	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	—	+
33.	Guanidyl	306	O	79	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₈ S ₂	—	+
34.	α -Pyridyl	265	O	77	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₇ S ₂	+	—
35.	Pyrimidyl	270	O	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₈ S ₂	+	—
36.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	194	O	74	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₈ S ₂	+	—
37.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	248	O	73	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₈ S ₂	+	—
38.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	237	Y	76	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₈ S ₂	+	+
39.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	274	O	73	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₈ S ₃	+++	—
40.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	260	O	72	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₇ S ₂	+	—

TABLE 2—3-METHYL-5-(*p*-ETHYLPHENYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

 (Ar = *p*-ethylphenyl)

S.No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
R ₁ = H							
1.	H	240	YO	74	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆ S	—	—
2.	Acetyl	230	O	71	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₆ S	+	+
3.	Phenyl	212	OR	72	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₆ S	—	—
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	225	R	72	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₆ S	+	—
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	194	O	73	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₆ S	+	+
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	217	O	72	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₆ S	+	+
7.	Guanidyl	263	OR	75	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₇ S	—	+
8.	α -Pyridyl	268	O	73	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₆ S	+	+
9.	Pyrimidyl	278	O	78	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₇ S	+	+
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	218	R	73	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₇ S	+	+
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	216	Y	74	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₇ S	+	+
12.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	225	OR	75	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₇ S	++	+
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-Thiadiazolyl	278	O	77	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₇ S ₂	++	—
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	236	O	73	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₆ S	+	+
R ₁ = Ph							
15.	H	218	OR	74	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₅ S	—	—
16.	Acetyl	225	YO	75	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₅ S	++	+
17.	Phenyl	180	OR	70	C ₃₀ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₅ S	—	—
18.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	221	R	70	C ₃₁ H ₂₉ O ₂ N ₅ S	—	+
19.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	202	R	72	C ₃₁ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₅ S	—	—
20.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	182	R	74	C ₃₁ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₅ S	—	—
21.	Guanidyl	180	OR	75	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₇ S	—	+
22.	α -Pyridyl	220	O	71	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₆ S	—	+
23.	Pyrimidyl	204	RO	77	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₇ S	—	+
24.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	172	R	75	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ O ₂ N ₇ S	—	—
25.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	193	YO	74	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ O ₂ N ₇ S	+	—
26.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-Thiadiazolyl	167	YO	72	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₇ S ₂	++	—
27.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	205	YO	69	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ O ₃ N ₆ S	+	—
R ₁ = Thiocarbamido							
28.	H	228	YO	76	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	—	—
29.	Acetyl	195	O	70	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	++	+
30.	Phenyl	195	O	69	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	—	—
31.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	222	YO	70	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	—	+
32.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	222	R	72	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	—	—
33.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	228	O	74	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	—	—
34.	Guanidyl	265	O	72	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	—	+
35.	α -Pyridyl	250	YO	74	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₇ S ₂	—	+
36.	Pyrimidyl	242	YO	78	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	—	+
37.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	220	R	74	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	—	—
38.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	232	YO	75	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	+	—
39.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-Thiadiazolyl	278	YO	76	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₆ S ₃	+++	—
40.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	234	YO	69	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₇ S ₂	+	—

(a) There was good agreement between percentages of C and H found and required.

(b) B = Brown; O = Orange; R = Red; Y = Yellow.

References

- G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 351; 1975, 52, 960.
- AJAYA KABRA, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 989.
- C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 985.
- G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Indian J. Pharm.* 1975, 37, 147.
- G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Indian J. Microbiology*, (in press).
- C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 181.
- C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Def. Sci. J.*, 1975, 25, 97.
- BRITISH PHARMACOPAEA, Pharmaceutical Press, London, 1953, p. 796.